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THE INFLUENCE OF THE PROGRESSION POLICY ON EDUCATORS' JOB SATISFACTION

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Abstract

The aim of this article is to delve into the rationale driving the advancement of learners and emphasise the significance of implementing the Progression Policy (PP) in schools in South Africa. Additionally, it seeks to examine educators' perspectives and experiences regarding the PP, explore potential measures to support educators in effectively implementing this policy through instructional activities, and investigate the effect of the PP on educators' job satisfaction in secondary schools. Drawing upon Vroom's expectancy theory, this study employs an explanatory research approach to gain a comprehensive understanding of how the PP influences educators' job satisfaction. Purposeful and convenient sampling were utilised to gather responses from 32 secondary school educators through questionnaires. The findings reveal that the implementation of the PP has a discernible effect on educators' job satisfaction, with data indicating a notable decrease in satisfaction post-implementation compared to pre-implementation.

Keywords: Progression, Job satisfaction, Implementation, Academic performance, Policies

Introduction

Education policies across the world are developed to address educational issues, but the effect of these policy implementations on educators remains a challenge. The education system is one of the few systems that requires continuous change and adaptability, and because of that, educators are faced with the reality of being subjected to intensification and accountability which leads to decreased job satisfaction and ultimately negatively affects their profession (Yim & Moses, 2016). Lekalakala (2013) reports that the Department of Basic Education (DBE) expects educators to effectively implement the policies they assign to them yet the same educators who are expected to implement these policies are not involved in their formulation by the Education Policy Unit of the DBE. Educators play an integral part in ensuring the successful implementation of introduced education policies because they are responsible for a good classroom climate and appropriate activities. Thus, educator's attitude regarding any policy can either promote or hinder the success of the policy (Bornman & Donohue, 2013).

Learners' academic performance has been the focus for the development of schools since the beginning of education (Likando, 2017). Learners' poor academic performance has also been an obstacle in the South African education system for years (Moyo & Maseko, 2016). For the past two decades there has been no significant improvement in South African learners' achievement. Their academic performance remains poor, even after a significant investment in the schooling system (Prinsloo, Rogers & Harvey, 2018). The South African education system has identified high repetition rates in grades 10-12 (Further Education and Training (FET) phase) and therefore, the outmost impact of learners' academic performance is felt specifically in the FET phase (Kika & Kotze, 2019). As in other countries, attempts were made in South Africa to remedy the unnecessary drop-out of learners in schools. This was done through the formation of the progression policy (PP) (Mogale & Modipane, 2021). Progression is a mechanism designed to move learners from grade to grade to avoid having a learner retained in a phase for more than 4 years (DBE, 2012). Studies have shown the relationship between learners' academic performance and educators' motivation and job satisfaction (Iwu, Gwija, Benedict & Tengeh, 2013). Poor

motivation on the part of educators may lead to poor learner performance and vice versa. Leepo (2015) further mentions that educators in South Africa face difficulties related to the expectation to perform with the very minimum support from the DBE and lack of resources. These difficulties lead to learners' attendance problems, high dropout rate and grade repetition.

The purpose of this article is therefore to examine educators' perspective and experiences regarding the PP and to understand how the implementation of the PP influences educators' job satisfaction in trying to improve the academic performance of learners in secondary schools. The information of this article can assist the DBE to provide the necessary support to educators to effectively implement the PP and to devise strategies to improve educators' job satisfaction. This in turn can contribute to the improvement of such learners' academic performance.

Progression Policy

The PP can be regarded as one of South Africa's key transformation vehicles within the education sector (Munje & Maarman, 2016). The aim of the PP is to address poor learner performance in education, to improve the education system and to provide adequate access to education for underperforming learners. If learners are forced to remain in a grade because of failure to achieve the promotional requirements, the DBE will be faced with high levels of learner dropout from the education system (Stott, Dreyer, & Venter, 2015).

The DBE (2011:xi) defines progression as follows: "Progression means the advancement of a learner from one grade to the next, excluding Grade R, in spite of the learner not having complied with all the promotion requirements". The PP was introduced in 2013 to assist learners who had repeated a grade at least once but not more than four times in a single phase to move on to the next grade. This is done on condition that the underperformance of the learner carried from the previous grade is dealt with in the next grade. The policy was fully implemented in 2015 (Kika & Kotze, 2019). For a learner to be eligible for progression, the grade progression and promotion requirements are outlined below:

- The learner has not met the promotion criteria for either Grade 10 or Grade 11 and had to repeat one of these grades.
- The learner has achieved a passing grade in their home language and three additional subjects.
- The school attendance was consistent, with no more than 20 days of absence.
- The learner has fulfilled the school's requirements for assessments in all subjects.

Academic Performance

Progressed learners become the victims of poor motivation, effort and performance which hinder their academic achievement (Polirstok, 2017). The expertise of educators to impart knowledge to learners is in most cases shown by the academic achievement of learners (Muema, Mulwa & Mailu, 2018). Poor academic performance has been an obstacle in the education system for years specifically in secondary school. Therefore, learners, parents, schools, and educators' involvement in learners' academic work should not be taken for granted as it affects the learners' academic outcomes (Moyo & Maseko, 2016).

Ngema (2016) mentions that although the DBE has put remedial measures in place such as extra classes and visits by the departmental officials, the problem still persists. This is an indication that the DBE has not identified the main cause of learners' poor performance. The general idea is that learners fail to perform in their senior phase because primary schools do not build a solid educational foundation in basic subjects such as numeracy and literacy (Bojuwoye, Moletsane, Stofile, Moolla & Sylvester, 2014). When learners are motivated and supported in their studies by their parents and educators, their academic performance improves (Muhammad, Bakar, Mijinyawa & Halabi, 2015). The academic performance of learners has an impact on the social development of a country; academic performance of learners is evaluated when employers want to hire them or for university enrolment. Thus, if educators feel that they are teaching learners who cannot perform academically and will probably stay at home after Grade 12, they will be less motivated, dissatisfied and stressed. It is also evident that learners' academic performance and educators' job satisfaction are related (Kosgei, Mise, Odera & Ayugi, 2013). Programmes designed to support the curriculum and facilitate learner advancement are subject to influences that encourage engagement and stimulate learning. These influences, acting as stimuli, have the potential to enhance the effectiveness of curriculum support initiatives and consequently drive policy implementation. Ultimately, this can result in improved academic performance for learners, culminating in successful completion of Grade 12 (Mogale & Malatji, 2023).

School Attendance

High absenteeism of learners from school is closely linked with high failure and low retention rates of learners (Coetzee & Venter, 2016). A relationship between learner attendance and academic performance has been identified, meaning that when learner attendance improves so will their academic achievement (Komakech, 2015). Factors such as gender, age, grade and barriers to learning needs and importantly learner's poor attendance affect learner performance negatively and absenteeism leads to an early high dropout rate of learners (Mafa, 2018). The above-mentioned facts are the reasons that the DBE implemented PP to keep learners in school with the assurance that if they meet the requirement of attending school regularly even if they fail, they might be eligible for progression. General academic performance, classroom practices, anticipated learner behaviour and school attendance are compromised for many progressed learners (Hlasa, 2022).

Job Satisfaction

One of the challenges that the DBE is faced with is to maintain job satisfaction amongst educators. For this article, the definition of job satisfaction provided by Sahito and Vaisanen (2017, p.6) was used: "Job satisfaction is the collection of feelings, beliefs and attitudes about the job, especially about work and its kinds and about co-workers, supervisors, subordinates and pay". Factors that can affect an educators' job satisfaction are numerous and diverse and can be classified into three categories, namely organisational, cognitive and affective factors (Malinen & Savolainen, 2016). The various policies under which teachers work can have a tremendous effect on their job satisfaction (Uke, et al., 2023). The progression policy is no exception. Admiraal (2023) states that feelings of distress and stressful circumstances in teaching and classroom management are significant factors influencing variations in teachers' job satisfaction. There exists a negative correlation between teachers' experiences of burnout, learner misbehaviour, and low learner motivation, and their overall job satisfaction. Various factors can play a role.

Organisational Factors

Two organisational factors that affect the educators' job satisfaction are teacher empowerment and working conditions.

Teacher empowerment is based on three dimensions: control over content, control over methods and potential effect on school policy. Therefore, empowerment is related to teacher participation in the decision-making process (Aliakbari & Amoli, 2016). Balyer, Özcan and Yildiz (2017) believe that when education authorities (such as DBE in SA) aim to reach solutions to problems related to the effectiveness of the school, such as the effective implementation of the PP by educators, their primary focus should be the empowerment of educators. Therefore, Squire-Kelly (2012) in accordance with Vroom's theory mentions that when educators' expectation of their empowerment is met, they experience an increase in job satisfaction. Benefits of empowering educators can be increasing self-confidence, educator growth and fostering collaboration whilst eliminating alienation and bureaucracy.

The evaluation of an educator's working conditions does not only affect whether he/she will stay in their current post or school, but it also influences job satisfaction (Allen, 2014). Poor working conditions in schools contribute both to learners' poor academic performance and to educators' dissatisfaction which leads to poor teaching performance (Ohide & Mbogo, 2017). Nkosi and Magubane (2019) report that the PP is at the centre of the educators' unfavourable working conditions.

Cognitive Factors

Cognitive factors that have an influence on educators' job satisfaction are self-efficacy and collective efficacy (Malinen & Savolainen, 2016). Educators with high levels of self-efficacy have the ability to perform better in educational settings and are more willing to use different teaching methods with the intention of satisfying learners' needs (Karabiyik & Korumaz, 2014). Furthermore, educators' sense of self-efficacy is positively associated with their job satisfaction (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2017). Educators' self-efficacy positively fosters improved relationships between educators and their learners. This positive influence can therefore assist in achieving improved academic performance when learners (promoted or progressed) and educators work together (Miller, Ramirez & Murdock, 2017). It is to be expected that as educators (novice or experienced) have different personality traits so will their sense of self-efficacy be different when dealing with classroom management, how they engage their learners particularly progressed learners and their use of different instructional strategies. If educators believe in a policy such as the PP, they are more likely to positively influence learners' academic performance and achieve improved job satisfaction (Perera, Granziera & McIlveen, 2018).

Affective Factors

Burnout and work-related stress are affective factors which influence educators' job satisfaction (Malinen & Savolainen, 2016). When educators experience burnout, they are less likely to find satisfaction in their work and this affects their work engagement. Berry (2011) adds that the inability of educators to achieve goals, like attaining a reasonable pass rate of learners who have been promoted to the next grade solely by achieving the promotional requirements is identified as an attribute among educators who experience burnout.

Job stress is one of the most intriguing issues dealt with in the modern world. The fact that educators are not satisfied in their work may be a stressor which leads to a decrease in their job performance, job satisfaction and ultimately negatively impacts the functionality of the whole school (Yaacob & Long, 2015). Hence, Vroom's theory highlights the fact that educators' behaviour is influenced by their expected outcomes. Thus, if educators put more effort into their job performance and yet the outcomes are not representative of the effort, this could lead to stress and ultimately dissatisfaction. Putting more effort into teaching learners who at the end of the year fail and must be progressed could make educators minimise the effort they put in the process of teaching and learning, a sign of demotivation and dissatisfaction. Educators' job satisfaction is thus a core component of the survival of a school and known to have a direct influence on its effectiveness and efficiency (Motonga-Manga, Flotman, & Cilliers, 2018).

Theoretical Framework

Vroom's Expectancy Theory

Vroom's Expectancy Theory provides the theoretical framework for this study. Vroom indicated that performance is a function of an individual's knowledge, skills, abilities, personality, and experiences. Furthermore, the theory assumes that behaviour is a result of deliberate choices from alternatives aimed at maximizing pleasure and minimizing pain. The Expectancy Theory postulates that motivation is a product of expectancy, instrumentality, and valence (Vroom, 1964). Human actions and choices are driven by their desires and affection for certain outcomes, their belief that specific actions produce these out-comes, and that certain primary outcomes are associated with secondary outcomes (Vroom, 1964).

According to Purvis, Zagenczyk and McCray (2015), Vroom's Expectancy Theory describes the process people go through when making a personal evaluation of their environment and actions they take because of their expectations. The expectancy theory is based on the belief that educators' behaviour is motivated by the level of expected outcomes they desire. Furthermore, the theory emphasises the tendency of educators to behave in a particular manner which is dependent on the expectation that their behaviour will yield specific outcomes and will also be influenced by the attractiveness of the outcome (Suciu, Mortan & Lazar, 2013). The Expectancy Theory is a process theory of motivation that views motivation as a function of an individual's perception of the environment and expectations based on these perceptions (Marczak & Yawson, 2021).

Method

This is an empirical study that employed an explanatory research design. The study opted for an explanatory research design since its goal was to comprehend the connection between various variables and factors, such as the implementation of the PP, and its impact on educator job satisfaction. (George & Merkus, 2021). The study was underpinned by an interpretivist paradigm. The study's population consisted of educators working in secondary schools within the Lejweleputswa education district. A purposive sampling strategy was employed to select the research sites and participants. This ensured that participants had relevant knowledge of the phenomenon being researched (Edmonds & Kennedy, 2017). The sample of this study totalled 32 secondary school educators. The sample allowed participants to provide relevant information regarding the research questions of this study.

This study employed a questionnaire which was completed independently by participants. The questionnaire contained three sections: Section A to obtain biographical data and Section B to obtain information on the progression policy with some open-ended questions to gather opinions of the sampled teachers. Section C contained a standardised questionnaire, Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ), to test educators job satisfaction as well as 10 additional questions relating to workload and burnout. The MSQ consisted of 20 questions related to before and 20 questions related to after the implementation of the PP. A Likert scale of 1 – 5 were used where 1 = 'Not Satisfied' and 5 = 'Extremely Satisfied'.

The determined Cronbach's alpha of 0.957 indicates that job satisfaction before the implementation of the PP showed that the scale had a high level of internal consistency. Job satisfaction after the implementation of the PP was determined by a Cronbach's alpha of 0.960. The data collected in the study underwent analysis using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software. Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012) emphasise the

importance of aligning the choice of data analysis with other methodological decisions, as outlined in the research onion framework. Descriptive data were presented through tables and graphs, with SPSS utilised for data analysis and interpretation. SPSS holds significant popularity in academic and business settings (Arkkelin, 2014). Inferential statistics were employed to assess statistical significance pre- and post-implementation of the PP on participants' job satisfaction levels. In this particular study, ANOVA was performed across four distinct teacher age brackets to ascertain any associations or variances in job satisfaction before and after PP implementation among these age cohorts.

Ethical clearance and permission to conduct this study were obtained from the Humanities Research Ethics and Innovation Committee of the university and the Free State Department of Basic Education. A letter granting permission was received from the principal while letters of consent were obtained from the participants. The participants were given a clear explanation of the study's nature and objectives, and participation was purely voluntary. Pseudonyms were used to keep the participants' names and responses anonymous.

Findings

The questionnaire and results were used to answer the following research questions:

- What are educators' perspectives of the PP?
- How was educators' job satisfaction level influenced by the implementation of the PP?

Educators' Perspectives on the Implementation of PP

Table 1 indicates that most participants (53.1%) believed that the implementation of the PP has enabled undeserving learners to progress, resulting in a lack of motivation among learners, demoralisation among educators, and challenges for learners in passing Grade 12. Conversely, a smaller fraction of participants (3.1%) believe that the policy's implementation has contributed to reducing the high dropout rate among learners.

Table 1: Personal views of educators on the implementation of the PP

	Frequency	% of all participants (n=32)
Undeserving learners get progressed	17	53,1%
Learners don't have a will to work	8	25,0%
Teachers become discouraged	4	12,5%
Struggle to pass Grade 12	2	6,3%
Some progressed learners improve in higher grades	5	15,6%
Teachers teach irrespective of PP	4	12,5%
Criteria needs to be reviewed	3	9,4%
Lack of support/guidance for educators and learners	2	6,3%
Not producing quality future learners	2	6,3%
Reduces the high drop put rate	1	3,1%
Prevents having 30-year-old learners	1	3,1%
Not answered	1	3,1%

In Table 2, the most encouraging aspect of the PP for educators while teaching, is that it motivates some learners to work harder and demonstrate their capabilities (46.9%). The most positive experience of the PP that educators encounter during teaching was that some learners become motivated/work harder to prove themselves (46.9%). When educators have such positive experiences, they are more inclined to assist progresses learners. In addition, educators have reported that they put more effort into progressed learners; this is indicated by 12.5% which is another positive experience they encounter.

Table 2: Educators' positive experiences of the PP in everyday teaching

	Frequency	% of all participants (n=32)
Some learners are motivated/work harder to prove themselves	15	46,9%
Learner's needs are taken into consideration	4	12,5%
Teachers put more effort into progressed learners	4	12,5%
None/not answered	8	25,0%

Table 3 indicates that 50.0% of the participants noted the most unfavourable aspect of the PP as the unfair or undeserving progression of learners to the next grade, followed by 43.8% of participants who observed that learners lack effort. A total of 9.4% of participants stated that the PP has generated progressed learners who are so demotivated that they engage in truancy, leading to unsatisfactory academic outcomes.

Table 3: Educators' negative perceptions on progression

	Frequency	% of all participants (n=32)
Learners unfairly/undeservingly move onto the next grade	16	50,0%
Learners do not put in any effort	14	43,8%
Progressed learners require extra time and attention	4	12,5%
Progressed learners' lower results	3	9,4%
Learners bunk school	3	9,4%
Progressed learners lack prior content knowledge	2	6,3%
Schools are expected to put their own implementation strategies in place	2	6,3%
None/Not answered	1	3,1%

Discussion of the Preceding Results

Some educators have indicated that they have positive views about the PP. Educators mentioned that the PP has played a role in preventing the possibility of keeping learners in the education system even when the learner is much older than his/her peers. In support of this view the literature has stated that the PP was implemented with the notion of moving learners through the education system with their peers (Kika & Kotze, 2019). Throughout this study, diverse perspectives among educators regarding the implementation of the PP have emerged. The data reveals that most educators expressed negative sentiments about the PP. Some educators contended that the policy has allowed undeserving learners to progress, and even though some learners have been granted the opportunity for progression, they still do not exhibit the willingness to seize this opportunity and put in the required effort. Polirstok (2017) observes that if progressed learners are not inclined to change their mindset and utilise the opportunity for progression, they may succumb to low motivation and achieve poor academic results. These results have left educators disheartened, leading them to advocate for a reconsideration of this policy.

Job Satisfaction

Participants mentioned that their understanding of job satisfaction was the enjoyment one gets out of their job/being passionate about their job (59,4%). To be valued or appreciated was not seen as job satisfaction (3.1%). Table 4 summarises descriptive statistics on PP and job satisfaction. To present the data in simplified form, the data on the Table have been collapsed into YES and NO responses.

Table 4: Summary of descriptive statistics

Item	Yes (%)	No (%)
Job satisfaction affects educators' commitment	96.6	3.4
Job stress associated with job satisfaction	83.9	16.1
Progression policy increased workload	93.3	6.7
Experienced burnout since implementation	77.4	22.6
Progression policy influences job satisfaction	83.3	16.7
Compared to other school factors, PP influenced job satisfaction the most	76.7	23.3
Assistance from DBE with regards to PP can improve job satisfaction	78.6	21.4

Job Satisfaction Differences Before and After Implementation of the PP

Table 5 indicates that the most visible difference before and after the implementation of the PP was the time required from educators (34.4%), most specifically because of additional administration and extra classes/attention for progressed learners. Educators stated that the implementation of the PP came with added responsibility and at 18.8% it also affected learners negatively because they do not take their work seriously nor do they complete it.

Table 5: Job satisfaction differences before and after the implementation of the PP

	Frequency	% of all participants (n=32)
Requires additional time	11	34,4%
More administration	4	12,5%
Extra classes/ attention	4	12,5%
Learners' behaviour changed	6	18,8%
Negative: Do not do their work/take it seriously	4	12,5%
Positive: Work harder	1	3,1%
Learners lack content knowledge	5	15,6%
Teachers are demotivated	4	12,5%
Lower pass rate and lower quality	3	9,4%
Dropout rates dropped	3	9,4%
Lack of support regarding the policy	3	9,4%
Not answered	3	9,4%

Table 6: Statistical Summary of educators' overall job satisfaction before and after the implementation of PP

How satisfied are you with: On a scale of 1 (not satisfied) to 5 (extremely satisfied)	Before PP Mean ± SD	After PP Mean ± SD	
Your workload	3,61 ± 1,09	1,93 ± 0,98	
The opportunity to work alone on the job	3,48 ± 1,00	2,19 ± 0,91	
The opportunity to do different things from time to time	3,35 ± 1,05	2,16 ± 0,86	
The opportunity to be 'somebody' in the community	3,35 ± 0,99	2,48 ± 1,09	
The way your Principal (SMT) handled educators	3,29 ± 0,94	2,48 ± 1,09	
The competence of your Principal (SMT) in making decisions	3,13 ± 0,89	2,52 ± 1,24	
Being able to do things that didn't go against your conscience	2,71 ± 1,13	2,19 ± 1,01	
The way your job provided for steady employment	3,03 ± 0,98	2,45 ± 0,96	
The opportunity to do things for other people	3,10 ± 1,01	2,19 ± 1,01	
The opportunity to tell people what to do	3,13 ± 1,04	2,35 ± 1,02	
The opportunity to do something that makes use of your abilities	3,32 ± 1,14	2,42 ± 1,26	
The way schools' policies are put into practice	3,23 ± 1,12	2,06 ± 0,89	
Your salary and the amount of work you did	3,19 ± 1,06	2,03 ± 1,09	
The opportunities for promotion on this job	3,10 ± 1,04	2,16 ± 0,86	
The freedom to use your own judgment	3,39 ± 1,06	2,16 ± 1,22	
The opportunity to try your own teaching methods	3,44 ± 1,05	2,41 ± 1,21	
The working conditions	3,25 ± 1,05	2,06 ± 1,03	
The way your co-workers got along with each other	3,39 ± 1,05	2,23 ± 1,09	
The praise you got for doing a good job	3,60 ± 1,16	2,37 ± 1,19	
The feeling of accomplishment you got from teaching	3,53 ± 0,86	2,43 ± 1,10	
Overall job satisfaction	3,29 ± 1,40	2,27 ± 0,82	<i>p</i> <0,001

Discussion of the Preceding Results

For this study, it is crucial to grasp the changes that educators have experienced before and after the introduction of the PP, particularly concerning their job satisfaction. The data reveals predominantly negative effects on educators' post-implementation. Most educators indicated that their job commitment is significantly influenced by their level of job satisfaction. When dissatisfied with their teaching career, it becomes challenging for them to maintain commitment. This highlights the importance of job satisfaction in minimizing absenteeism and maximizing teaching dedication. Moreover, the data indicates that educators attribute the stress they endure at work to their job satisfaction. In other words, dissatisfaction in their teaching role may heighten their stress levels. This aligns with existing literature (Malinen & Savolainen, 2016) suggesting that job stress impacts educators' job satisfaction, often due to factors like increased workload associated with the PP, subsequently affecting job performance.

Educators have expressed experiencing burnout since the PP's implementation, further influencing their job satisfaction. Studies such as the one from Westphal, Kalinowski, Hoferichter and Vock (2022), have linked increased workload to heightened burnout among educators. Dissatisfaction with the workload imposed by the PP significantly contributes to decreased job satisfaction among educators. Vroom's theory emphasizes that educators are motivated by the belief that effort leads to rewarding outcomes, hence increased workload and burnout leading to dissatisfaction. Crucially, the data underscores that the implementation of the PP has indeed impacted educators' job satisfaction negatively. Even when considering other school factors, the PP stands out as the primary source of educators' dissatisfaction. Educators believe that with assistance from the DBE and the school, they can achieve the objectives of the PP while maintaining job satisfaction.

Table 6 demonstrates a significant shift in educator satisfaction with their workload pre- and post PP introduction, with dissatisfaction increasing notably. Additionally, educators expressed dissatisfaction with the execution of school policies following the PP's implementation, along with reduced contentment regarding promotion opportunities within their job. Overall, the comprehensive job satisfaction data strongly indicates that the PP has had an adverse effect on educators' overall job satisfaction.

Inferential Statistics: Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ)

Results from independent T-Test

Table 7 shows that there was not a statistically significant difference in job satisfaction after PP implementation between participants with positive and negative PP opinions, ($t [29] = -1,96, p > 0,05$, two tailed). There were 24 participants with a negative opinion of the PP and seven participants with a positive opinion. One participant did not answer question B12, therefore could not be associated with a positive or negative view and was not included in this specific analysis. Job satisfaction after the PP implementation was higher for those with a positive PP opinion ($2,89 \pm 0,70$) than those with a negative opinion ($2,24 \pm 0,79$). The mean difference was (-0.65); however, this difference was not statistically significant, and the magnitude of the difference is small ($d = 0.12$).

Table 7: T-Test results for job satisfaction after PP implementation among participants with differing opinions on PP

N=32

Variables	n	M	SD	t	df	p	MD	95% CI	d
Satisfaction after PP implementation				-1.96	29	0,06	-0.65	-1.32 to 0.03	0.12
Negative opinion towards PP	24	2,24	0.79						
Positive opinion towards PP	7	2,89	0.70						

After the participants completed the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ), the result was documented and explained separately according to each question. Figure 1 combines all the separate results to present the overall view of participants regarding their job satisfaction before and after the implementation of the PP. This graph indicates that before PP, the average job satisfaction was at 3.3 (satisfied). After PP, the average job satisfaction was at 2.3 (somewhat satisfied).

Figure 1: The overall job satisfaction before/after the implementation of the PP

Conclusions

Educators are familiar with the PP and fully informed about the implications and details. The implementation of the PP has impacted educators' job satisfaction, suggesting that it has led to dissatisfaction among educators in their teaching roles. Furthermore, it is stressed that even after considering other school-related factors, the primary cause of educators' job dissatisfaction is attributed to the implementation of the PP. For educators their job commitment is seriously influenced by their job satisfaction and when they are not satisfied in their teaching career, it is hard for them to be committed. This indicates that job satisfaction is important for educators to minimise absenteeism and maximise their teaching obligation. Vroom's theory outlines that educators' behaviour is motivated by the level of expected outcomes they desire. Thus, if educators expect to attain satisfaction from their job and that is not achieved, it may lead to lack of commitment.

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